

RETAIN PROJECT

#OER2 Rights Retention policies

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With these resources, you will be able to

1. Define rights retention and rights retention policy.
2. Understand the benefits of a rights retention policy.
3. Grasp what form a policy could take.
4. Inspire how an institution can develop a policy.
5. Manage how to develop a RR policy.
6. Identify different approaches to the topic.

**Learning
objectives**

1. Define rights retention

Understanding rights retention

WE UNDERSTAND RIGHTS RETENTION AS...

- The action to retain sufficient rights for academic works to enable them to be openly accessible and reusable preferably immediately.
 - ✓ When publishing open access, authors retain the right to waive any condition or limitation when using licences different to CC BY

INSTITUTIONAL RIGHTS RETENTION POLICY MEANS...

- An expressed position setting out the practice of retaining sufficient rights for academic works of an institution's employees to make the work immediately openly accessible and reusable.

Understanding Rights Retention

AS AN AUTHOR YOUR RIGHTS ARE...

Moral rights	Economic rights
Examples	Examples
<p>Right of attribution, i.e. the right to be acknowledged as the author of a work</p> <p>Right of integrity, i.e. the right to preserve a work against any change that could harm the creator's reputation</p>	<p>Right to reproduce the work in any format</p> <p>Right to distribute a physical copy of the work</p> <p>Right to communicate the work to the public (e.g. by making it available online)</p> <p>Right to translation or adaptation of the work</p>
Ownership	Ownership
Moral rights are inalienable	<p>Can be transferred to others, fully or partially</p> <p>They expire (in most legal systems) 70 years after the author's death, the work then enters the public domain</p>

Who is the original copyright holder?

- Different legal regimes lead to different rules
- In some legal systems, it must always be a natural person, and not a legal person
- In some legal systems, there are special provisions related to “works for hire” which may apply to scholarly works
 - ◆ Author(s) will always retain their moral rights, the economic rights can belong to the employer.
 - ◆ Most academic institutions usually (informally or explicitly) leave decisions about copyright to the authors, who can decide how and where to publish their works and to whom to transfer their copyright
- The author can transfer their economic rights or give the exploitation right to others
 - ◆ As an exclusive or non-exclusive right
 - ◆ As a right that is unlimited or limited in terms of content, time or space

2. Understanding institutional rights retention policies

What are the benefits of a rights retention (RR) policy?

INSTITUTIONS ADOPT RIGHTS RETENTION POLICIES TO...

- ✓ accelerate the uptake of immediate Open Access in the institution while acknowledging the importance of keeping rights and the risks of transferring all rights by default.
- ✓ ensure that the researchers and the institutions they are affiliated with retain sufficient rights to the outputs of their research to make them immediately openly accessible and reusable in different contexts.
- ✓ clarify what rights researchers have and how they are implemented in practice.
- ✓ protect their intellectual property and fulfill funder requirements.
- ✓ seek to improve accessibility to to all published research outputs whilst making Open Access more affordable.

What form could a RR policy take?

VARIOUS FORMS OF POLICY DEPEND ON THE CONTEXT...

- Policies may be standalone or incorporated into existing policy stacks.
 - They may mandate specific behaviours or simply recommend them and offer support.
 - There are variations in how open licensing is required or recommended.
- ✓ The most effective policy type and level is unavoidably linked to context and how they are formulated.
- ✓ Institutional policies are often part of a raft of measures that are developed in parallel by stakeholders to achieve greater access to research within a particular country.

What form could a policy take?

Policy scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May be a standalone policy or incorporated into broader policies covering Open Access, a publishing policy, or Intellectual Property
Nature of mandate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some policies establish a right for institutions or authors; some mandate researchers to exercise or retain specific rights; some make recommendations to researchers; some policies only offer guidance for researchers seeking to meet a funder mandate. • Researchers may be able to opt out of the policy if they deem that they are unable to publish their research effectively.
Content covered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May cover only journal articles, a wider range of written scholarly output, or non-written outputs from research including data and software. • May require an Author Accepted Manuscript or Version of Record.
Authors covered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May cover just faculty employed conducting research only, or extended to non-faculty, including postgraduate students
Open licensing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May require CC BY, some other combination of CC licences, or may not require any specific licence type.

3. Developing institutional rights retention policies

- How to develop a RR policy
- How to persuade an institution to develop a policy

How to develop a RR policy

SET A GOAL TO...

- ✓ ensure the accessibility of research outputs in subject areas where funding for article processing charges (APCs) or large-scale OA agreements are not in place.
- ✓ reduce the amount of the overall cost to an institution of making its researchers' outputs openly accessible.
- ✓ encourage researchers not to choose licensing options that transfer reuse rights to the publisher.
- ✓ ... other

Factors to consider when developing a policy

EXTERNAL FACTORS ARE...

- **Legislation:** copyright law, contract law, legislation on scientific research and innovation
- **National policy environment:** National science policies, including Open Science, national funder policies, and the research assessment framework.
- **Publishing culture:** Publishing infrastructure, primary route to Open Access: whether through Green OA (self-archiving in repositories), Gold OA (publishing in fully open-access journals) or transformative agreements (TAs), the strength of the culture around the researchers' freedom to choose where to publish, and attitudes to Open licensing.

Factors to consider when developing a policy

INTERNAL FACTORS ARE...

- **Existing policy stack:** any formalised approach to rights retention will need to consider integration and harmonisation with (at least) existing policies on Open Access or Open Science, Intellectual Property and Copyright, and Publishing and the dissemination of research.
- **The attitude of leadership:** while some leaders are eager to adopt Open Access and Open Science trends, others are more risk-averse and require more advocacy to overcome resistance.
- **Capacity for support:** support researchers in understanding the funder requirements placed on them and in negotiation with publishers.
- **Approval processes** through committee structures, researcher unions or representation is a consistent step in the process of adoption and has a particular impact on the time it takes to launch and implement policies

How to develop a RR policy

RECOMMENDATIONS TO START UP THE PROCESS...

- Set a goal
- Seek to map out the different factors in play in their environment that will affect the extent and nature of the policy.
- Do not seek perfection. No such thing exists and much progress can be made even in challenging environments and jurisdictions.
- Seek other interested parties within and outside your institution who can help pool resources and accelerate progress. Joining forces can mobilise change faster.
- Seek legal advice, it will help you understand your options and the risks that need to be addressed.
- Engagement with researchers to appeal to them remains a key factor.

How to develop a RR policy

5 KEY ELEMENTS ARE ...

1. **Legal advice** to understand current options and determine how far a policy can go in order to be successfully implemented under existing contract and copyright laws.
2. **Coalition-building:** build alliances both within and outside the institution. Internally, engage faculty across disciplines, institutional leadership, within and outside the library. Externally, collaborate with legal experts, open science advocates, civil society organizations, policymakers, and umbrella bodies to strengthen support.
3. **Collaboration:** facilitate alliances among stakeholders to accelerate progress and pool resources.
4. **Copying:** adapt successful policies from other institutions and fit them to your local context and your institutional needs.
5. **Engagement:** highlight the benefits of policies that protect researchers' rights and academic freedom, while considering whether an opt-out or opt-in approach is best for diverse needs.

4. Implementing institutional rights retention policies

- Examples of institutional rights retention policies across Europe

The current situation in Europe

- ✓ Institutions in the UK & Norway have been the main adopters of rights retention policies since 2022.
- ✓ Countries in Europe are reviewing the basis on which institutional policies could be established and the extent of the benefits they could bring. There is a focus on developing the national policy environment and legislation where it is possible to do so, often alongside awareness-raising initiatives.
- ✓ Collaborative initiatives can promote rights retention and establish clear common ground but still allow for considerable variation in policies at the institutional level. The N8 collaboration in the UK demonstrates this well, as do the cross-institutional approaches facilitated by the Finnish University Libraries Network (FUN) and the Universities of the Netherlands.

Institutional rights retention policies

	University of York		
Policy title	Research Publications and Open Access Policy	Research publications and Copyright policy	Principles of Open Access to Academic publications
Mandate or guidance	Mandate	Mandate	Mandate
Content covered	All scholarly articles (including original research articles, review articles, and articles published in conference proceedings)	Journal articles, encouraged for all scholarly outputs	Journal articles, encouraged for all scholarly outputs
Authors covered	Researchers and staff members	Academic staff	Employees and students
Opt in or opt out	Opt out	Opt out	Opt out
Process of engagement/ approval from Faculty	Employment contract requires assignment of non-exclusive license to institution	Employment contract requires assignment of non-exclusive licence to institution	UiT given permission to make their academic works available; Rector has the legal responsibility for interpreting this policy, resolving disputes about its interpretation
Formal communication with publishers	Letter from institution notifying publishers of prior licence, supported by other institutions across the N8.	Letter from institution notifying publishers of prior licence Insertion of language by authors in manuscripts recommended	Policy itself provides notification to publishers
Article type	AAM	VoR or AAM	VoR or AAM
Specified mechanisms	Open access digital repository	Institutional repository	Institutional repository
Licence applied	CC BY	CC BY	Creative Commons licence

N8 Consortia: Rights Retention statement

Universities of Durham, Lancaster, Leeds, Liverpool, Manchester, Newcastle, Sheffield and York

Example of alliances to accelerate progress

The N8 Research Partnership represents the research-intensive universities of the North of England. 12% of all UK academics work at N8 universities as well as almost 200,000 students. The N8 is one of the strongest regional academic consortia in the UK and believes the time is now right to make a co-ordinated statement on the rights held by its academics over their research.

N8 Research Partnership – Statement on Rights Retention

Universities of Durham, Lancaster, Leeds, Liverpool, Manchester, Newcastle, Sheffield, York

The N8 Research Partnership represents the research-intensive universities of the North of England. 12% of all UK academics work at N8 universities as well as almost 200,000 students. The N8 is one of the strongest regional academic consortia in the UK and believes the time is now right to make a coordinated statement on the rights held by our academics over their research.

- *The world is changing fast.* In April 2022, the UKRI made it mandatory for all research published in journals to be made immediately available. This can be via fully OA or transformative Gold journals' APC charges or journals released on a transitional Read & Publish deal without APC charges. It can also be via depositing the author accepted manuscript and making it openly available without embargo.
- *Researchers need to retain their rights.* In order to achieve this third route to open access researchers need to be able to apply a CC BY licence and place their accepted manuscript in an institutional or other preferred repository. This must now be done without embargo granted to any publisher.
- *Some publishers are no longer compliant.* A number of publishers do not accept that a researcher's original rights should be retained by them. Practically speaking this means that publishers may not accept manuscripts where an application has been made for a CC BY licence and the researcher has clearly stated that they own their research.
- *Rights Retention is only mandatory for certain publishers but recommended for all.* Each N8 university will have its own position which may supersede the publisher's requirements, but ultimately if a researcher is able to publish via an APC to a Gold journal or in a journal covered by a Read & Publish deal then researchers do not need to assert their rights. However, it is strongly recommended that researchers do not by default transfer intellectual property rights to publishers and do use a Rights Retention statement as standard practice.
- *The N8 Statement on Rights Retention supports our researchers.* In coordinating the N8 universities' position on rights retention we seek to support all our academics if they find themselves caught between funder's and publisher's policies. Each N8 university will have its own policy but this statement aims to support all our researchers in retaining their rights.
- *It is funders, not publishers who stipulate regulations for grant awards.* Similarly it is universities, not publishers who provide the environment which allows research to take place.
- *The N8 fully supports the shift to open access.* It has never been more important for the world to have access to research and the N8 Research Consortium believes that asserting Rights Retention at an individual or research group level can benefit wider society.

The N8 is working through its PVC's for Research, Research Offices, Legal Departments and Libraries to support our researchers not only in research activity but in global open access to that knowledge.

An example of a Rights Retention policy

UiT The Arctic University of Norway

For employees and students wishing to publish in academic publication channels that have subscription-based access, UiT's infrastructure for self-archiving (Green OA) shall ensure Open Access to the academic literature.

UiT's Rights Retention Strategy

UiT is introducing a Rights Retention Strategy to facilitate that all academic literature from UiT, not just that with external funding, is made available with Green OA.

As of 1 January 2022, the following applies: Irrespective of the publication channel, full-text versions of research articles written by employees and students at UiT must be uploaded (deposited) continuously in the national register (currently called Cristin).

- If a Gold OA channel has been used, the publisher's PDF (the published version, Version of Record) must be uploaded.
- If a closed subscription-based channel has been used that does not allow self-archiving of the publisher's PDF, the latest peer-reviewed manuscript version (the author's accepted manuscript, "postprint") must be uploaded.

The requirement about uploading full-text versions applies to peer-reviewed articles in journals and anthologies. However, UiT also encourages authors to upload other genres of academic literature, including books (monographs), popular science articles, newspaper articles and other research-based dissemination activities. This will not have retrospective effect and applies to all articles published on or after 1 January 2022. In the long term, the proportion of deposited and accessible articles may be of significance for UiT's allocation of results-based budgets to the faculties.

All full-text versions uploaded will be made openly available in the institution's repository (currently called Munin). Authors wishing to reserve themselves against the full-text version being made available in Munin may apply for an exemption. Such applications shall be sent using a separate solution via UiT's website.

By failing to apply for an exemption from the rule concerning Open Access, UiT's employees and students give the institution permission to make full-text versions available in the open research archive (currently called Munin) under a Creative Commons license, in line with prevailing international practice within Green OA infrastructure.²

UiT wishes to point out to publishers of academic literature that the institution's employees and students hereby give UiT permission to make their academic works available online under a Creative Commons license, provided that the individual right to request an exception is not exercised.

The Rector has the legal responsibility for interpreting this policy, resolving disputes about its interpretation and ensuring the processing of applications for exemptions from the rule concerning open access.

UiT has introduced a Rights Retention Strategy to facilitate that all academic literature from UiT, especially for researchers without access to funding for APCs, is made available with Green OA.

An example of a Rights Retention policy

Research Publications & Copyright Policy

1. The University of Edinburgh confirms the current practice that members of staff own the copyright to their scholarly works.
2. Upon acceptance of publication each staff member with a responsibility for research agrees to grant the University of Edinburgh a non-exclusive, irrevocable, worldwide licence to make manuscripts of their scholarly articles publicly available under the terms of a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence, or a more permissive licence.
3. After granting the licence each staff member with a responsibility for research will provide an electronic copy of the accepted manuscript (AM) of each article at no charge to the appropriate representative of the University of Edinburgh in an appropriate electronic format (such as PDF).
4. The University of Edinburgh will deposit the AM in a digital repository, with article metadata usually available immediately upon deposit and the AM being made accessible to the public on the date of first online publication (or the conference end date for conference proceedings) under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence.
5. This policy applies to all scholarly articles, including conference proceedings, authored or co-authored while the person is a staff member of The University of Edinburgh, which includes any third party content where rights in that content have been secured. Any articles submitted, or accepted, for publication before the adoption of this policy are exempt.

The University of Edinburgh confirms the current practice that members of staff own the copyright to their scholarly works.

Slovenia - An example of a Rights Retention approach in law

DECREE on the implementation of scientific research work in accordance with the principles of open science, May 2023

IV. MANAGEMENT OF COPYRIGHT IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE PRINCIPLES OF OPEN SCIENCE

Article 6

(Copyright management of scientific publications)

(1) Copyright in scientific publications may only be transferred to third parties on a non-exclusive basis by the authors of the scientific publications or by their employers where the rights are transferred to them.

(2) The authors of scientific publications or their employers, where copyright is transferred to them by law, shall publish scientific publications under an open licence that allows anyone to freely use, modify and share the scientific publication in accordance with the principles of scientific research ethics (e.g. a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence and Attribution-ShareAlike (CC BY-SA) licence or equivalent).

(3) Funders shall include the requirements referred to in paragraphs one and two of this Article in calls and contracts for the co-funding of scientific research activities.

(4) Monographs and scientific publications of comparable length, if peer-reviewed or if third parties hold any rights in them, may be published under a licence that restricts further commercial use or adaptation of the work (e.g. the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial (CC BY-NC) licence, which restricts further commercial use, and the Creative Commons Attribution NoDerivatives (CC BY-ND) licence, which prohibits derivatives, or their equivalents).

(5) Metadata on research publications shall be made public. If copyright, rights related to copyright or other rights of the author arise in the metadata of research publications under the law governing copyright and related rights, the metadata shall be made available under a licence whereby the authors waive their copyright, related rights and other rights as authors to the fullest extent permitted by law (e.g. the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) licence, or, where this is not possible, under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence).

Copyright in scientific publications may only be transferred to third parties on a non-exclusive basis by the authors of the scientific publications or by their employers where the rights are transferred to them.

Next step: Institutional rights retention policy implementation

Rights Retention Resources

- KR21 Rights retention position paper
<https://www.knowledgerights21.org/wp-content/uploads/KR21-Rights-Retention-Position-Paper-September-2024.pdf>
- RetainYourRights campaign
<https://www.knowledgerights21.org/retainyourrights/>
- Rights Retention Helper
https://sparceurope.org/?page_id=11364&preview=true
- SPARC Europe. Retain project webpage
<https://sparceurope.org/what-we-do/open-access/copyright/project-retain/>
- University rights-retention OA policies
https://oad.simmons.edu/oadwiki/University_rights-retention_OA_policies

Thank you

SPARC Europe
<https://sparceurope.org/>

RETAIN PROJECT
[https://sparceurope.org/what-we-do/open-access/copyright/
project-retain/](https://sparceurope.org/what-we-do/open-access/copyright/project-retain/)